

Brazil and China bilateral trade: an analysis of economic and environmental impacts by MARIO

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Executive Summary

This executive summary encapsulates key findings from a comprehensive analysis of the bilateral trade dynamics between Brazil and China, emphasizing economic and environmental dimensions. Noteworthy insights emerged from scenario analyses, particularly in Scenario_2 and Scenario_3, where the reduction of sectorial emissions successfully aligned with the heightened Chinese demand for exports, resulting in decreased emissions embodied in trade.

Critical to the sustainable progression of this bilateral trade relationship is the recommendation to institute a compensation system for emissions in both nations. Grounded in principles of emissions responsibility, this system would inform the development of commercial policies aligned with the imperative of addressing climate change.

As a strategic course of action, policymakers are urged to design a framework of commercial policies that establish offset goals correlating with the surge in export demand. A tangible example involves China contributing to financing Brazilian environmental programs, such as the Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation in Developing Countries (REDD+). Simultaneously, Brazil can reciprocate by fostering sectors conducive to the energy transition in China or by engaging in collaborative projects aimed at enhancing energy efficiency.

By adopting such measures, policymakers can foster a symbiotic relationship between economic growth and environmental sustainability, ensuring that the bilateral trade between Brazil and China evolves in harmony with the imperatives of climate change mitigation and ecological responsibility.

1. Introduction

Since 2004, China's dynamism has had an impact on Brazil's export structure, leading to a significant increase in demand for commodities - mainly mining, livestock and cereals. On the one hand, the increase in demand for commodities contributed to the generation of a trade surplus, with an average export growth rate of 15% since 2010. On the other hand, this movement favoured an increase in the market share of commodity goods in exports, leading to an effect known as the "re-commoditisation" of Brazil's export structure (Bertola, Ocampo, 2012).

From an environmental point of view, the advance of commodity sectors has been associated with increased deforestation and other negative externalities. Also, the “re-commoditisation” promotes a low level of investment in industrial sectors, which means a drop in productivity and energy efficiency. Brazil is therefore faced with the challenge of promoting an industrialization model that is compatible with contemporary environmental demands, while also controlling deforestation and improving environmental efficiency.

In this sense, considering the economic and environmental impacts resulting from the demands of international trade, the following research questions drives this analysis: What are the main economic and environmental effects, in terms of GHG emissions, of China's demand on Brazil's production structure? And, as a policymaker, what are the conditions for implementing a system of offsetting emissions embedded in trade for the Brazil-China partnership? Those questions have the role to promote the discussion about the emissions impact associated with bilateral trade and pointed out the importance to consider a system of compensation for emissions.

Therefore, after this introduction, the paper is divided into three further sections. The second section presents the methodology and database used in the analysis. The third section presents the main results, and the fourth section proposes a discussion of the analysis based on the results. Finally, the paper concludes with some final considerations and policy implications.

2. Methodology

The paper applies a method of decomposing value added into trade flows based on Johnson and Noguera (2012) and Chen et al. (2021). The method is developed on the Multiregional (MRIO) matrix and managed by the Multifunctional Assessment of Regions through Input-Output (MARIO), an open-source Python-based platform designed to process input-output models (Tahavori et al., 2023).

We propose to estimate the value added and GHG emissions embodied in flows of goods and services traded from Brazil to China in 2022. The exercise aims to show how economic outcomes, in terms of value added, are linked to environmental outcomes, in terms of GHG emissions. The period was chosen because it is a more recent version of the data available.

The modelling process of MARIO is given by the following steps:

1. Aggregation of industries and satellite accounts according to the research question criterion and to facilitate data handling.
2. Estimate the value added and GHG emissions embodied in forward linkages transactions from Brazil to China.
3. Estimate scenarios for sectoral demand shocks and sectoral emissions reduction

The scenarios were defined as:

Scenario	Definition
Baseline	Estimate the value added and GHG emissions of Brazilian exports to China.
Scenario_1	Increase in 15% of Chinese demand for exports from Brazil.

Scenario_2	A 15% increase in Chinese demand for exports from Brazil and a 15% reduction in Brazil's total sectoral emissions.
Scenario_3	Increased in 5% of Chinese demand for exports from Brazil and reduction of 15% on Brazilian total sectorial emissions.

Fonte: Own elaboration.

2.1 Database

EXIOBASE version 3 is an environmentally extended multi-regional input-output (EE MRIO) database with high suitability for environmental analysis. The tables range from 1995 to 2011 - but with various nowcasts to extend the data to 2020 - for 44 countries (28 EU Member States plus 16 major economies) and five rest of the world regions, 163 industries and 200 commodities. The data provide a consistent framework for tracking emissions, resource use and other environmental externalities along supply chains, thus linking consumption patterns to production processes elsewhere (Stadler et al., 2018).

3. Results

Figure 1 shows the results of the value added, in € (Euro), embodied in the sectoral forward linkages from Brazil to China, for selected sectors that present results higher than the sectoral average. In general, we observed that the increase in Chinese demand promoted the increase in value added for the sectors, mainly for "Other services". In other words, it means that Brazilian export sectors receive positive economic feedback from Chinese demand in terms of the value added embodied in this production.

Figure 1 – Forward linkages, in value added (in EUR)

Source: Own elaboration.

In Figure 2, we have shown the GHG emissions embodied in Brazil's forward linkages with China. First, we could see in Scenario_1 that the simple increase in Chinese demand pushes to higher sectoral emissions on these relations, mainly for

"Other services", "Water transport" and "Electronics and electrical manufacturing", respectively. However, Scenario_2 and Scenario_3 show that it is possible to accommodate the increase in Chinese demand for Brazilian exports with lower levels of emissions than the Baseline, if this could be offset by the reduction in total sectoral emissions.

Figure 2 – Forward linkages, in GHG emissions (in TCO2e)

Source: Own elaboration.

Therefore, the results show that reducing sectoral emissions intensity – which means, in the Brazilian case, improving energy efficiency in the manufacturing and transport sectors, and reducing emissions associated with food production – is mandatory in order to reduce the level of GHG emissions to meet China's demand for exports.

4. Discussion and Policy Insights

The paper identifies and discusses the characteristics of the bilateral trade between Brazil and China in economic and environmental terms. Based on the shock analysis and results, we highlight that Scenario_2 and Scenario_3, which include the reduction of total sectoral emissions, were able to match the increase in Chinese demand for exports with lower levels of emissions embodied in trade.

Thus, we believe that the conditions for the implementation of an emissions offset system between Brazil and China are the application of the principles of responsibility for emissions as a driver for the design of trade policies. Lenzen and Murray (2010), Marques et al. (2012), Zhang (2013) and Zhang et al. (2020) discuss and apply a theoretical conceptualisation to the practice of assigning responsibility for emissions using four principles:

- (i) Production-Based Responsibility (PBR), which assigns responsibility to producers for all emissions generated by production in the domestic economy, which are usually defined as territorial emissions;

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- (ii) Consumption-based responsibility (CBR), which assigns responsibility to demand-side components (households, government, importers) for emissions embodied in trade flows, usually defined as the ecological footprint of traded goods and services;
 - (iii) Income-based responsibility (IBR), responsibility attributed to the providers of primary inputs, who derive income from emitting activities;
 - (iv) Shared responsibility (SR), which refers to the allocation of responsibility between all actors involved (producers, consumers and those who receive the income).

Considering this conceptualisation and the specificities of bilateral trade between Brazil and China, we highlight that principle as a reference to design commercial policies with a focus on reducing emissions embodied in trade. As a policymaker, one could design a set of commercial policies that set some offset targets related to the increase in demand for exports. For example, China could contribute by financing some Brazilian environmental programmes - such as the Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation in Developing Countries (REDD+) (Euler, 2015), or by developing some project of technology transfer to improve energy efficiency in Brazil - as well as Brazil could contribute by stimulating the sectors that favour the energy transition in China.

These findings reinforce the importance of a multi-dimensional view for policy making in the context of climate change. Therefore, for future research and improvements, it is possible to explore the structural decomposition method to track GHG emissions by type of trade transaction (intermediate or final), which is relevant in the context of global value chains, also when working in some case studies for the higher emission intensive sectors.

5. Conclusion

In summary, this paper examines the economic and environmental aspects of bilateral trade between Brazil and China. Notably, Scenario_2 and Scenario_3 demonstrate that reducing sectoral emissions aligns with increased Chinese export demand while lowering emissions in trade. Emphasizing environmental responsibility, implementing a compensation system based on emission principles is crucial for crafting trade policies that align with emission reduction goals.

This study highlights the need for a multidimensional approach in climate-conscious policymaking. Future research could explore the structural decomposition method to track emissions by trade transaction type, particularly in global value chains, and case studies about higher emission-intensive sectors. In conclusion, advocating for a dynamic policy framework, this study encourages ongoing efforts to ensure sustainable international trade.

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Appendice A

The analysis is driven by the decomposition of value added into trade flows of goods and services, based on the fundamentals of Leontief (1936) and the structural decomposition analysis method developed in Chen et al. (2021).

From the beginning, we consider the Leontief's classical production system for an open economy:

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{A}^D\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{Y}^D + \mathbf{A}^F\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{Y}^F = \mathbf{A}^D\mathbf{X} + \mathbf{Y}^D + \mathbf{E}, \quad (1)$$

where the total output $\mathbf{X}$ is determined by intermediate consumption as a fixed proportion of the value of output, expressed by the technical coefficient, $\mathbf{A}$; and final demand variations, $\mathbf{Y}$; considering all the intermediary and final external relations, $\mathbf{E}$ (Miller and Blair, 2009). In this sense, $\mathbf{A}^D$ is a domestic technical coefficient, a diagonal block $\text{NG} \times \text{NG}$ matrix of domestic input coefficients, given by:

$$\mathbf{A}^D = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}^{SS} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{A}^{SS} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \mathbf{A}^{gg} \end{bmatrix}$$

Thus, we can define the block matrix of input coefficients that is off the main diagonal as $\mathbf{A}^F$, and is therefore a block matrix of imported input coefficients NGxNG, expressed as:

$$\mathbf{A}^F = \mathbf{A} - \mathbf{A}^D = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \mathbf{A}^{su} & \dots & \mathbf{A}^{st} \\ \mathbf{A}^{us} & 0 & \dots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{A}^{ts} & \dots & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

So, based on these definitions, we can write the domestic and the global version of the Leontief inverse matrix, according to their respective technical coefficient matrices, as follows:

$$\text{Domestic version: } \mathbf{L} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}^D)^{-1}, \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Global version: } \mathbf{B} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})^{-1}, \quad (3)$$

The division between $\mathbf{A}^D$ and $\mathbf{A}^F$ provides a simultaneous decomposition of production, both between intermediate and final goods, and by the location of production and consumption, which is relevant for GVC analysis. Thus, using the value-added estimation method by Johnson and Noguera (2012) and Timmer *et al.* (2013) we can characterize the value added embodied in the countries' production, which is expressed as follows:

$$\widehat{\mathbf{V}}\widehat{\mathbf{Y}} + \widehat{\mathbf{V}}\mathbf{A}\widehat{\mathbf{Y}} + \widehat{\mathbf{V}}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{A}\widehat{\mathbf{Y}} + \dots = \widehat{\mathbf{V}}(\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{A} + \mathbf{A}\mathbf{A} + \dots)\widehat{\mathbf{Y}} = \widehat{\mathbf{V}}(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})^{-1}\widehat{\mathbf{Y}} = \widehat{\mathbf{V}}\mathbf{B}\widehat{\mathbf{Y}} \quad (4)$$

In this equation, the term $\mathbf{V} = \{v_i^k\} = \left\{ \frac{v_i^k}{x_i^k} \right\}$ refers to the value-added vector of sector i of country k , divided by the total product x of the same industry; and $\widehat{\mathbf{V}}$ is a diagonal matrix of $\mathbf{V}$. The term $\mathbf{B}$ is the global version of Leontief's inverse matrix and $\widehat{\mathbf{Y}}$ is a diagonal matrix of global final demand. Each element of the matrix $\widehat{\mathbf{V}}\mathbf{B}\widehat{\mathbf{Y}}$ represents the value-added (VA) of an industry in its home country that is used directly or indirectly in the production of final goods and services in a given country/sector. The sum of the row and column elements of the matrix is the total VA (direct and indirect) of the industry in the country embodied in the final products produced by sector i in country k .

Thus, the sum of the rows and columns of the matrix $\widehat{\mathbf{V}}\mathbf{B}\widehat{\mathbf{Y}}$ represent the forward and backward linkages between sectors in different countries, where we have:

- *Backward linkages*: the columns sum, $\sum_{i,s} v_i^s b_{ij}^{rs} y_j^r = y_j$, equals the value of the final goods produced by sector j in country r , which refers to the purchases of this sector/country from another sector/country.
- *Forward linkages*: the row sum, $\sum_{j,r} v_i^s b_{ij}^{rs} y_j^r = v_i$, equals the total value added by sector i in country s , showing the sales of this sector/country to another sector/country.

Based on these definitions, for the analysis of bilateral trade, the $\mathbf{B}$ matrix is given by intermediary transactions from country r to country s , and $\mathbf{Y}$ is final demand of country s .

To obtain the results in terms of carbon emissions, the $\mathbf{C} = \{c_i^k\} = \left\{ \frac{c_i^k}{x_i^k} \right\}$, which refers to the carbon vector of sector i of country k , divided by the total product x of the same industry, is introduced on the equation (4).

